

Influence of halogen substitution on the electronic structure and reactivity of bexarotene-derived hydrazones: insights from DFT descriptors^{*}

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Abstract

Bexarotene is a clinically approved anticancer agent belonging to the retinoid class. Integrating the retinoid scaffold with a hydrazone moiety represents a promising strategy for modulating electronic properties relevant to receptor binding and desired biological activity. However, the electronic effects of halogen substitution within the retinoid–hydrazone framework have not been systematically studied. To address this gap, this study investigates the effects of substituent position, halogen type, and halogen load on the electronic structure and reactivity of a series of bexarotene-derived hydrazones. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were carried out for six bexarotene–hydrazone derivatives (V1–V6), enabling the evaluation of frontier molecular orbital energies and global reactivity descriptors. In the series, V2 emerged as the strongest electron acceptor, demonstrating the highest electronegativity, the largest electrophilicity index, and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) energy. The *para*-bromo analogue V4 displayed a similarly narrow highest occupied molecular orbital–lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (HOMO–LUMO) gap, although it demonstrated more donor-like behavior. The dichloro derivative V3, on the other hand, had the widest energy gap and the highest hardness and was recognized as the most electronically stable derivative. The *ortho*-chloro derivative V6 showed strong similarity to V3 in several descriptors, showing that substituent position can rival the number of halogens in determining reactivity. Overall, these electronic patterns provide a basis for future drug design, demonstrating how targeted substituent modification within the bexarotene–hydrazone scaffold can guide the development of new molecules with more favorable physicochemical properties.

Keywords

Bexarotene, bexarotene-derived hydrazones, biological activity, DFT study, reactivity descriptors

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Introduction

Retinoids represent a diverse class of compounds that include both naturally occurring derivatives of vitamin A and an extensive range of synthetic analogues (Farol and Hymes 2004). Their structural resemblance to vitamin A enables them to participate in biological processes essential for maintaining cellular homeostasis. The association between vitamin A deficiency and carcinogenesis was first recognized in the 1920s, when pioneering investigations demonstrated that insufficient vitamin A levels could induce profound tissue alterations, including hyperplasia, metaplasia, and dysplasia—lesions strongly associated with increased preneoplastic potential (Hunsu et al. 2021). These early findings firmly established retinoids as important modulators of cancer prevention and underscored their biological relevance (Noy 2000).

In recent decades, convincing evidence has accumulated that retinoids exert a much more profound effect on fully transformed and invasive neoplastic cells than was initially assumed. It has gradually become clear that these compounds not only limit the rate of cell division but also promote differentiation processes in a wide range of tumor lines. This dual effect is explained primarily by their ability to engage specific nuclear receptors that control the transcription of genes involved in cell cycle regulation, programmed cell death, and phenotypic maturation (Altucci and Gronemeyer 2001). Interestingly, as mechanistic studies have deepened, a far more complex picture of the action of retinoids has emerged. Their actions extend far beyond simply limiting proliferation. Increasing evidence suggests that retinoids influence diverse signaling networks, positioning them as important modulators of a wide range of transcriptional programs involved in oncogenic transformation and progression. It is this functional multifacetedness that is gradually shifting the understanding of retinoids from classical vitamin A derivatives to more complex molecular tools with the potential to redirect pathological cellular states. The evolution in knowledge thus described has significantly expanded their therapeutic perspectives and supported the idea that retinoids can occupy a more central place in the strategy for the control and modification of neoplastic processes (Uray et al. 2016).

Retinoids exhibit their biological and pharmacological effects largely by interacting with several nuclear receptors and forming functional heterodimers with retinoic acid receptors (RARs) (Reynolds et al. 2003). Although retinoids are most often associated with dermatological practice, especially in the treatment of acne, psoriasis, and various manifestations of photodamage, in recent years their role in oncology has become significantly more tangible (Napoli et al. 2020). Data are constantly accumulating showing that these molecules have potential far beyond the treatment of skin disorders. Both local and systemic forms of application demonstrate favorable results in a number of premalignant and malignant lesions, which gradually establish retinoids as promising agents not only for chemo-

prophylaxis but also as complementary therapeutic agents in oncology protocols. This expansion of their clinical significance once again emphasizes the versatile nature of this group of substances. These findings have encouraged ongoing efforts to explore and modify retinoid structures in search of compounds with improved receptor selectivity (Tripathi et al. 2019).

Among synthetic retinoids, bexarotene has become one of the most notable examples (Fig. 1). It is the first compound designed to act selectively on retinoid X receptors (RXRs), a group of agents now known as rexinoids, and it was developed with a clear focus on oncological therapy—most prominently for cutaneous T-cell lymphoma (Querfeld et al. 2006). The emergence of rexinoids marks an important step forward in retinoid-based drug development, as this class enables more targeted engagement of nuclear receptor pathways and allows for greater therapeutic precision. Because bexarotene binds predominantly to RXRs and shows minimal activation of retinoic acid receptors (RARs), it tends to produce fewer off-target effects and generally offers a better safety profile than earlier retinoid drugs. These characteristics have encouraged ongoing efforts to create newer rexinoids with improved receptor selectivity (Leal et al. 2021).

Figure 1. Chemical structure of bexarotene.

The therapeutic relevance of retinoids has therefore stimulated extensive synthetic work aimed at developing new analogues. Over time, this has led to a significant expansion of structural diversity in retinoid chemistry. A multitude of derivatives have been designed and synthesized that differ in their physicochemical characteristics and in the way they affect cellular mechanisms (Fritz et al. 2011). This increasing diversity reflects not only the drive to optimize pharmacological properties but also the constant need for molecules capable of recognizing specific subtypes of nuclear receptors or modulating transcriptional pathways with greater specificity and precision. In a sense, the development of these structures follows the logic of biology itself—the more complex the regulatory networks, the more finely tuned the molecular tools that influence them must be. An important element in these design efforts is the deliberate modification of the core retinoid scaffold, which has shown considerable flexibility toward structural refinement. Introducing heterocyclic fragments, polar substituents, or other functional groups

has proven particularly effective in enhancing receptor affinity and optimizing ligand orientation within the binding pocket (Hafeez et al. 2017).

Within this broader scientific context, hydrazones have gradually gained a more prominent place due to their pronounced structural flexibility and promising pharmacological profile (Shao et al. 2020). These compounds are distinguished by the characteristic azomethine bond ($-C=N-$), which places them in the Schiff base group, and in most cases they are prepared by condensation between primary amines and carbonyl-containing molecules. This relatively simple reaction leads to the formation of chemical frameworks that are easily modified, thus allowing the exploration of a variety of structures with potential biological activity. Incorporating a hydrazone moiety into bioactive molecules has been linked to a wide range of effects, such as anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant activities. The functional group itself offers several useful characteristics: the azomethine bond can take part in hydrogen bonding and allows π -electron delocalization, which often strengthens the interactions a molecule can form within protein-binding pockets. Furthermore, the somewhat dynamic nature of the imine bond gives the ligand an additional degree of conformational freedom. This feature may facilitate its more precise fit to the three-dimensional organization of the binding pockets in nuclear receptors, sometimes even allowing more efficient adaptation to specific microenvironmental changes within the receptor itself (Popiołek et al. 2017).

Hydrazides, which are the immediate precursors of hydrazones, also play an important role in shaping the favorable properties of these molecular scaffolds (Khattar et al. 2023). The hydrazide group adds polarity to the structure while still preserving a reasonable degree of lipophilicity, a balance that is particularly valuable for ligands designed to reach intracellular receptors such as the RXRs (Huang et al. 2016). Additionally, substituents attached to either the hydrazide or hydrazone segment can influence the electronic properties of the entire molecule (Rollas et al. 2007). By adjusting these substituent effects, it is possible to fine-tune electron distribution across the retinoid core, which in turn can affect how effectively the ligand engages in key interactions within the receptor-binding site (Senthilkumar et al. 2021).

Introducing hydrazone-forming groups into the bexarotene scaffold represents a logical approach for adjusting the electronic profile, hydrogen-bonding potential, and conformational flexibility of the parent compound. Such structural modifications can influence both the affinity and selectivity of the molecule toward RXR subtypes, opening a pathway to the development of newer retinoids with more refined structural and pharmacological properties. From a medicinal chemistry perspective, the hydrazone linkage is also highly advantageous synthetically, as it allows rapid diversification of the retinoid framework through condensation with a wide range of aldehydes. This, in turn, facilitates the design of a wide range of structurally diverse derivatives that can be rapidly subjected to subsequent biological evaluation (Velezheva et al. 2016).

The present study examines a series of newly synthesized hydrazone analogues of bexarotene. In the proposed synthetic strategy, bexarotene hydrazone functions as a flexible intermediate that allows for targeted modification of the core retinoid framework through condensation reactions with a variety of aldehydes. This approach provides a sequential introduction of structural variations, which in turn allows for a more refined assessment of the relationship between chemical modification and potential biological activity.

For the synthesis of the target compounds, bexarotene hydrazone was subjected to condensation with a selected series of aldehydes under classical hydrazone-forming conditions. Depending on the aldehyde reagent used, the corresponding bexarotene hydrazones were obtained. This approach ensured clean and consistent generation of the derivatives, allowing further comparison of their structural features and potential biological activities.

Although different bexarotene-derived hydrazones have been widely studied, the influence of structural variations, halogen type, and halogen load on their electronic properties and molecular reactivity has not been systematically studied. Consequently, the relationship between these modifications and potential biological activity remains unclear. A detailed density functional theory (DFT)-based study of these structural variations is needed to reveal how these substituents influence the electronic behavior and reactivity of this class of compounds.

Materials and methods

Studied molecules

In this study, a series of six bexarotene-based hydrazone derivatives (V1–V6) were designed to investigate how substituent position, halogen type, and halogen load influence the electronic structure and molecular reactivity. The six derivatives differ in the type and position of substituents attached to the phenyl ring of the hydrazone moiety. Three monochloro derivatives were included: V1 has a meta-chloro substituent (3-Cl), V5 has a para-chloro group (4-Cl), and V6 has an ortho-chloro substituent (2-Cl), allowing a systematic comparison of positional chlorine effects. V4 contains a para-bromo substituent, enabling direct evaluation of how halogen type, atomic size, and polarizability influence electronic structure. V2 contains a para-trifluoromethyl group ($-CF_3$), a stronger electron-withdrawing substituent than the para-chloro (V5) and para-bromo (V4) derivatives. Finally, the V3 derivative incorporates two ortho-chloro groups, which both enhance electron-withdrawing capacity and introduce steric hindrance in the derivative. Collectively, these structural variations allow a detailed study of how substituent position and type modulate DFT-derived descriptors that govern molecular reactivity, determine overall stability, and potential biological activity.

The described hydrazones were obtained by a multi-step synthesis, which begins with the reaction of bexarotene

methyl ester with hydrazine. This step leads to the formation of a hydrazone precursor. This precursor is important because it serves as an intermediate for the synthesis of various hydrazone derivatives of bexarotene (Agova et al. 2020).

Once the hydrazone precursor is formed, it is used directly in subsequent reactions without isolation.

In the next step, the hydrazone precursor reacts with a series of aldehydes. The selection of aldehydes is based on their reactivity and desired chemical properties, allowing the formation of a series of hydrazone derivatives. The reaction usually proceeds via condensation, yielding five

distinct hydrazone derivatives of bexarotene, depending on the aldehyde used. Overall, this multi-step synthetic strategy not only provides a route to generate various hydrazone derivatives but also demonstrates the flexibility and reactivity of hydrazones.

In addition to the hydrazone derivatives already described, this article also discusses a model hydrazone molecule (V6). Its molecule was not synthesized, but for better systematicity, its descriptors were calculated.

The structures of the studied molecules are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Chemical structures of the designed bexarotene hydrazone derivatives (V1–V6).

Computational methodology

All quantum-chemical calculations were performed with the Gaussian 16 software (Frisch et al. 2016). Molecular structures were constructed and generated using ChemCraft software (Andrienko 2010). Previous studies have demonstrated that the B3LYP functional in combination with the 6-311++g (d, p) basis set provides reliable results for hydrazone derivatives (Krishnan et al. 1980; Lee et al. 1988; Becke 1993, 1996; Adjissi et al. 2023; Tzankova et al. 2023). The structures of all bexarotene–hydrazone derivatives were initially optimized in the gas phase, and each geometry corresponded to a true minimum on the potential energy surface, as confirmed by the absence of imaginary frequencies. To account for solvation effects, subsequent calculations were carried out using the Polarizable Continuum Model (PCM) with water as the solvent ($\epsilon = 78$).

Theoretical framework

An essential variable in assessing molecular properties is the energy gap between the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO). The HOMO–LUMO energy gap (ΔE) is a measure of molecular stability and chemical reactivity. When the energy gap is smaller, molecules are softer, more polarizable, and more reactive (Fukui 1982). The ionization potential (IP), which corresponds to HOMO ionization, is the energy needed to remove an electron from a molecule. Electron affinity (EA) indicates the tendency of a molecule to undergo reduction. According to Koopmans' theorem, $IP = -E(\text{HOMO})$ and $EA = -E(\text{LUMO})$; therefore, compounds with lower IP values donate electrons more easily, and those with higher EA

demonstrate a stronger tendency to accept an electron (Koopmans 1934). Additional information on how resistant a molecule is to the redistribution of its electron density is provided by the descriptors global hardness (η) and softness (ζ). Hardness is defined as $\eta = \frac{1}{2} (E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO}))$, while softness is defined as $\zeta = 1/\eta$. Hard molecules exhibit higher energy gaps and resist charge deformation, whereas soft molecules (lower η , higher ζ) often take part in charge-transfer processes and are more easily polarized (Parr and Pearson 1983). The chemical potential (μ) is defined as $\mu = -\chi$ (where χ is electronegativity). A qualitative measure of a molecule's tendency to accept electron density is the electrophilicity index, defined as $\omega = \mu^2/2\eta$, which provides an effective measure of the overall electrophilic strength (Domingo et al. 2002). The maximum number of electrons that an electrophile or nucleophile can accept is defined as ΔN_{max} (Parr et al. 1999). The dipole moment is a key molecular property indicating how positive and negative charges are distributed in a molecule and represents an important molecular characteristic.

Results and discussion

Frontier molecular orbitals and reactivity descriptors of the studied hydrazones

The molecular orbitals, highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO), were computed using density functional theory to elucidate the electronic structure and reactivity of the studied bexarotene–hydrazone derivatives. All calculations were performed at the B3LYP/6-311++g (d, p) level of theory. The optimized geometries of the six

Figure 3. B3LYP/6-311++g (d, p) optimized structures of bexarotene–hydrazone derivatives.

bexarotene-based hydrazone derivatives (V1–V6) are shown in Fig. 3. In this work, the frontier molecular orbital energies and global reactivity descriptors (IP, EA, χ , η , μ , ζ , ω , ΔN_{\max}) were calculated for all six derivatives, each representing a specific structural modification: monochloro derivatives (V1, V5, and V6), para-substituent variation (V2 and V4), and increased halogen load (V3). This study design enables a systematic comparison of how substituent position, halogen nature, and degree of halogenation influence molecular reactivity. Further, the discussion centers on how the descriptors differentiate the molecules from one another, thus highlighting trends in electronic softness, electrophilicity, charge-transfer potential, reactivity, and stability. The computed values for all descriptors are summarized in Table 1.

Frontier molecular orbital analysis HOMO, LUMO, and HOMO–LUMO energy gap

The computed HOMO and LUMO energies (in eV) for the studied bexarotene-based hydrazone derivatives (V1–V6), together with the corresponding molecular descriptors, are presented in Table 1. Values for HOMO energies decrease in the following order: V4 (–6.25) > V6 (–6.32) \approx V1 (–6.32) \approx V2 (–6.32) > V5 (–6.33) \approx V3 (–6.33).

Among the studied molecules, V4 exhibits the highest HOMO energy and therefore is most willing to donate electrons, thus having a nucleophilic character. Conversely, V3 has the lowest HOMO and is least prone to oxidation. The subtle variations in HOMO energies of the monosubstituted chloro derivatives V1, V5, and V6 can be attributed to the position of the chlorine atom on the aromatic ring.

Table 1. HOMO and LUMO energies (eV), HOMO–LUMO energy gap (ΔE), ionization potential (IP), electron affinity (EA), electronegativity (χ), chemical hardness (η), chemical potential (μ), softness (ζ), electrophilicity index (ω), and maximum charge transfer index (ΔN_{\max}) for the studied bexarotene–hydrazone derivatives, computed in water (PCM) using the B3LYP/6-311++g (d, p) level of theory.

	E_{HOMO}	E_{LUMO}	ΔE	IP	EA	χ	η	μ	ζ	ω	ΔN_{\max}
V1	-6.32	-2.01	4.31	6.32	2.01	4.16	2.16	-4.16	0.46	4.02	1.93
V2	-6.32	-2.14	4.18	6.32	2.14	4.23	2.09	-4.23	0.48	4.29	2.03
V3	-6.33	-1.95	4.38	6.33	1.95	4.14	2.19	-4.14	0.46	3.90	1.89
V4	-6.25	-2.07	4.18	6.25	2.07	4.16	2.09	-4.16	0.48	4.13	1.99
V5	-6.33	-2.05	4.27	6.33	2.05	4.19	2.14	-4.19	0.47	4.11	1.96
V6	-6.32	-1.95	4.37	6.32	1.95	4.14	2.18	-4.14	0.46	3.92	1.89

The values of LUMO energies show the following trend (in eV): V2 (-2.14) < V4 (-2.07) < V5 (-2.05) < V1 (-2.01) < V6 (-1.95) \approx V3 (-1.95).

Here, V2 shows the most negative LUMO energy, followed by *para*-halogenated derivatives V4 and V5. V2 appears to be the molecule with the strongest electron-accepting capability among the series. In contrast, the *ortho*-substituted derivatives V3 (di-*ortho*-substituted) and V6 (mono-*ortho*-substituted) have the least negative LUMO energies, reflecting the weakest electron-accepting properties.

The HOMO–LUMO gap (ΔE) arranges the molecules studied as follows (in eV): V2 (4.18 eV) \approx V4 (4.18) < V5 (4.27) < V1 (4.31) < V6 (4.37) < V3 (4.38). The smallest ΔE values observed for V2 and V4 are expected to correspond to the most chemically reactive and electronically soft species. In contrast, V3, showing the largest ΔE , is expected to be the most rigid and electronically stable structure among the studied hydrazones.

Global reactivity descriptors

Ionization potential (IP) and electron affinity (EA)

The ionization potential (IP) and electron affinity (EA) values for the six hydrazone derivatives are summarized in Table 1. Among them, V4 displays the lowest IP, indicating that it is the easiest molecule to oxidize. In contrast, V3 and V5 possess the highest IP values and are therefore the most resistant to oxidation. Regarding electron affinity, V2 is the most favorable for electron uptake, with the highest EA value, consistent with its very low LUMO. Conversely, V3, with the lowest EA value, is the least prone to reduction.

Global reactivity parameters: (η , μ , χ , and ζ)

Global descriptors confirm the trend from frontier molecular orbital analysis. As presented in Table 1, V2 and V4 represent the softest and most polarizable hydrazones, characterized by relatively high electronegativity values and strongly negative chemical potentials. On the other hand, V3 is the hardest and least polarizable derivative, in agreement with its wide HOMO–LUMO gap. The three chloro isomers (V1, V5, and V6) show only subtle differences that fine-tune hardness but do not alter the overall hierarchy: V2 \approx V4 (most electronically flexible) \gg V3 (most rigid and stable).

Electrophilicity index (ω)

The electrophilicity index (ω), which measures the global tendency to accept electron density, integrating both chemical potential and hardness, exhibits the following trend: V3 (3.90) < V6 (3.92) < V1 (4.02) < V5 (4.11) < V4 (4.13) < V2 (4.29).

This trend highlights V2 as the strongest electrophile, followed by the *para*-substituted V4 and V5. The lower electrophilicity of V3 and V6 compared to other hydrazones is in line with their reduced electronegativity and higher hardness.

Maximum charge transfer index (ΔN_{\max})

Across the selected bexarotene-based hydrazones, all molecules displayed ΔN_{\max} values between 1.89 and 2.03, showing that the studied molecules can accept approximately two electrons. The order of ΔN_{\max} is V2 (2.03) > V4 (1.99) > V5 (1.96) > V1 (1.93) > V6 (1.89) \approx V3 (1.89).

The same pattern is observed: the highest capacity to accept charge is displayed by V2, while V3 and V6 accept the fewest electrons. Moreover, these values further highlight the enhanced electron-accepting properties of V2 relative to the rest of the series.

Dipole moment and polarity

The dipole moments in the series vary from 3.62 D (V4) up to 6.07 D (V2). Results are presented in Table 2. The most polar compound is V2, while V4 is the least polar. The polarity of molecules may influence solubility and interactions with polar environments. The relatively high dipole moments of V2, V3, and V5 suggest favorable interactions with polar binding pockets of enzymes. Conversely, the low dipole moment of V4 is more consistent with increased hydrophobicity and may favor interactions within environments of higher lipophilicity. Previous studies reported that hydrazone derivatives (V1–V5) exhibit poor water solubility but good solubility in methanol and DMSO, consistent with their mixed aromatic–hydrophobic character and moderate polarity.

Table 2. Calculated dipole moment (Debye, D) for the bexarotene-derived hydrazone derivatives.

	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6
Dipole moment (D)	4.04	6.07	5.46	3.62	5.29	4.60

Substituent position, halogen nature, and electronic reactivity trends in bexarotene hydrazones

Effect of chlorine position: V1 vs. V5 vs. V6

The HOMO energies of the monochloro derivatives (V1, V5, and V6) are very similar. The para-chloro isomer V5 has the most negative LUMO energy and the highest EA among the three, indicating increased electron-accepting ability. In contrast, the ortho-chloro isomer V6 has the least negative LUMO energy and the lowest EA value. Electronegativity (χ) and electrophilicity (ω) follow the same order, $V5 > V1 > V6$, demonstrating that para-substitution increases electrophilicity and charge-transfer capacity relative to meta (V1) and ortho (V6) substitution. Overall, the position of the chlorine atom modulates electrophilicity, electron uptake, hardness, and softness, most likely due to a combination of steric and conjugation effects.

Effect of the nature of the para substituent: V2 vs. V4

V2 and V4 differ in their para substituents, yet both have small HOMO–LUMO energy gaps, low hardness (η), and high softness (ζ), indicating strong reactivity profiles. The trifluoromethyl group ($-\text{CF}_3$) in V2 is a strong electron-withdrawing substituent, which stabilizes the LUMO, resulting in the most negative LUMO energy in the entire series. As a result, V2 displays the highest electronegativity (χ), the largest electrophilicity index (ω), and the highest ΔN_{max} of all compounds. In contrast, the para-bromo substituent in V4 favors HOMO elevation and donor ability. Overall, V2 can be described as the strongest electrophile and electron acceptor, while V4 is a softer, more donor-like halogen derivative. Both molecules are predicted to be highly reactive and good candidates for interactions that involve significant charge-transfer processes.

Effect of halogen load: monochloro (V1, V5, and V6) vs. dichloro (V3) derivative

A comparison of the monochloro hydrazone derivatives V1, V5, and V6 with the dichloro analogue V3 illustrates the influence of the halogen load on the electronic properties of the hydrazone scaffold. The dichloro derivative V3 has the lowest HOMO energy and the least negative LUMO energy, together with the largest HOMO–LUMO gap (ΔE) and the highest hardness (η), collectively identifying V3 as the least reactive derivative in the series. Interestingly, the monosubstituted ortho-chloro derivative V6 shows almost identical energetic characteristics to V3, highlighting that substituent position can be nearly as important as the number of halogens introduced in the aromatic moiety in determining the overall molecular reactivity. In contrast, the meta- and para-chloro derivatives V1 and V5 display smaller energy gaps and lower hardness values, making them more electrophilic and reactive than both V3 and V6. Thus, while the introduction of a second chlorine atom at the ortho positions makes V3 more inert,

chlorine substitution at the meta and para positions (V1 and V5) enhances electronic softness and reactivity.

Note that while DFT is commonly used to evaluate molecular descriptors, its accuracy depends on the choice of functional, basis set, and electron correlation. Additionally, Koopmans' theorem does not account for relaxation effects, which can cause deviations in ionization potentials (IP) and electron affinities (EA).

Conclusion

Bexarotene-based hydrazone derivatives represent a promising class of compounds whose electronic behavior is governed by the substituent position, halogen type, and halogen load on the aromatic ring. Based on the known anticancer properties of both the bexarotene and hydrazone scaffolds, the electronic patterns revealed in this study can guide the design of new analogues with optimized reactivity and enhanced therapeutic potential.

In this work, six bexarotene-based hydrazone derivatives were systematically investigated using DFT methods to clarify how structural variations, halogen type, and halogen load influence their electronic structure and molecular reactivity. Combining frontier molecular orbital analysis and global reactivity descriptors, we demonstrated that minor structural modifications within the aromatic ring of the hydrazone moiety result in significant electronic effects. Among the studied derivatives, V2 emerges as the strongest electron acceptor, exhibiting the lowest LUMO energy, highest electronegativity, and largest electrophilicity index. The para-bromo derivative V4 shows similarly small HOMO–LUMO gaps and high softness, indicating increased reactivity; however, it possesses a more donor-like nature. In contrast, V3 displays the lowest HOMO, the least negative LUMO, the broadest energy gap, and the highest hardness, designating it as the most rigid and electronically stable compound. The comparison of the monochloro isomers reveals that V5 exhibits enhanced electron-accepting capacity compared to V1 and V6. Notably, V6, despite being a monochlorinated derivative, closely resembles V3 in its energetic behavior, underscoring that substituent position may be as influential as the number of halogens in determining molecular reactivity. The trends in the dipole moments support these observations: the high polarity of V2 and the moderate polarity of V3 and V5 suggest interactions with polar biological environments, whereas V4, being the least polar within the series, may preferentially associate with hydrophobic regions of biomolecular targets.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, N.T. and S.G.; investigation, N.T., I.I., Y.U.; writing – original draft preparation, N.T., I.I., N.A., Y.U.; writing – review and editing, N.T., I.I., Y.U., S.G.; visualization, N.T. and K.M.; supervision, N.T., I.I., Y.U. and S.G.; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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